

Title: Maria Choir

1. PROGRAM NOTES

Interactive installation where a synthetic reproduction (using a timbre transfer model) of the Catalan singer Maria Arnal's voice harmonizes in real time what the visitor sings, forming a hybrid choir. The harmonization is performed by analysing the input voice and using different singing voice models (trained for different vocal registers). The harmonization process also includes a set of Maria Arnal's samples triggered accordingly to the result of the analysis of the input signal.

This work explores on the timber transfer possibilities to extend the human voice and reflects on how timber transfer techniques could offer new expressive possibilities.

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Interactive installation where a synthetic reproduction (using a timbre transfer model) of the Catalan singer Maria Arnal's voice harmonizes in real time what the visitor sings, forming a hybrid choir. The harmonization is performed by analysing the input voice and using different singing voice models (trained for different vocal registers). The harmonization process also includes a set of Maria Arnal's samples triggered accordingly to the result of the analysis of the input signal.

This work explores on the timber transfer possibilities to extend the human voice and reflects on how timber transfer techniques could offer new expressive possibilities.

Currently, the installation is on the AI Exhibition (<https://www.cccb.org/en/exhibitions/file/ai-artificial-intelligence/240941>) at the Centre for Contemporary Culture of Barcelona (CCCB). See the follow link for the description: <https://axolot.cat/maria-choir/>. For the NIME conference, we will present a simplified version (without visuals) focused on the sound processes.

Equipment Requirements:

We need:

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Music Proceedings of the International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression
NIME'24, 4-6 September, 2024, Utrecht, The Netherlands

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Author #1 et al.

- 4 (minimum 2) speakers and subwoofer
- Microphone stand

Optional (we can bring):

- Dynamic microphone + XLR cable
- Computer minimum specs: CPU AMD Ryzen 7 57000, GPU RTX-4070.

We will bring:

- Audio interface.

3. MEDIA LINK(S)

- <https://axolot.cat/aria-choir/>.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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